

SHAPING CRYPTOECONOMICS AS A NEW MARKET THROUGH BUSINESS MODEL INNOVATION

Omitted for blind review

Multiple reconfigurations of the proposed framework alongside its evolution

VERSION 1

Highlight: Approaching the concepts of market practices and value drivers.

VERSION 2

Highlight: Conceptualizing the different pathways for value creation.

VERSION 3

Highlight: Expanding the framework to encompass different levels of shaping.

VERSION 4

Highlight: Clarifying the process of translation and the designable elements.

